

PROVINCE OF BIELLA

POPULAR ANNUAL FINANCIAL REPORT

Fiscal Year Ended Dec. 31, 2021

INDEX

1) Message from technical member.....	1
2) About the province.....	2
3) Socio-demographic data.....	3
4) Public Administration Group.....	8
5) Consolidated Financial Statements.....	10
6) Ranking and Positioning.....	13
7) Policies:	
- European projects.....	16
- Social policies.....	17
- Educational policies.....	19
- Culture, sports and tourism policies.....	21
- Youth policies.....	24
- Equal opportunities policies.....	25
- Sustainable mobility policies.....	27
- Environmental and waste management policies.....	29
8) Methodological note.....	31
9) Dissemination plan.....	32
10) References.....	33

MESSAGE FROM THE TECHNICAL MEMBER

Franco Ferraris

President of Savings Bank
Foundation of Biella

The publishing of the Annual Report of OsservaBiella (Territorial Observatory of the Biella area) aspires to be a regular event that provides an opportunity for information and in-depth reflection on the territory.

As it approaches its second anniversary, the document has been supplemented with some indicators to offer an even more precise portrayal of the socioeconomic and cultural setting of the Biella area, always in the context of the United Nations' 2030 Agenda. This has been made possible by the increasingly active participation of the organizations that join OsservaBiella.

In the course of 2022, the Report has also begun to be used by local authorities, who have taken stock of data for inputs, projects, articles, and several activities in co-design have been initiated.

The Annual Report has therefore proved to be an important resource for the Province and its continuity over time will guarantee an ever greater in-depth and quality, allowing the Biella Savings Fund Foundation and local stakeholders to assist the community in realizing joint projects for a better future

ABOUT THE PROVINCE

The province of Biella, situated in the northwestern part of Italy within the region of Piemonte, is an area of remarkable cultural heritage and stunning natural beauty.

Its historical significance is deeply rooted, tracing back to the Roman era, and its cultural tapestry has been enriched by a diverse array of influences over the centuries.

From a geographical perspective, the Biellese Alps dominate the landscape, presenting an ideal environment for various outdoor pursuits, including hiking, skiing, and mountaineering.

The province of Biella, extended over an area of about 910 square kilometers, is bordered by the regions of Aosta Valley, the province of Vercelli and the province of Turin. It comprises a total of 74 municipalities. Among them stands the city of Biella, which is the provincial capital and important cultural and economic center, as well as Cossato and Vercelli, that are municipalities of significant size. The province also includes medium-sized towns such as Gaglianico, Trivero and Vigliano Biellese, where history and tradition are combined with modernity. In addition, there are Ponderano, Sordevolo and others, small villages each with its own character and peculiarities.

These province provides ample opportunities to engage with art and culture, thanks to the presence of museums, art gallerie and cultural events that pay tribute to its heritage.

The province of Biella is mostly renowned for its production of fine textiles, particularly high-quality wool. However, in addition to the textile secotr, the provincial economy is characterized by diversification, with manufacturing industry and tourism playing an important role.

With its awe-inspiring landscapes, esteemed textile heritage, and distinctive cultural legacy, the province of Biella offers an indelible and enriching experience to all its visitors.

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

The Report is introduced with a section that includes the most significant socio-demographic indicators related to the Province of Biella, the Piemonte Region and Italy. The chapter is intended to describe the local scenario as a whole and attempt to position it in relation to the regional and national context; it is also proposed as a useful reading key to the interpretation of the indicators contained in the other chapters.

In this first section, you may find information about the local population and its demographic structure. The main demographic indicators and statistics related to mortality, fecundity, and the presence of foreign and indigenous peoples are also included.

RESIDENT POPULATION

Source: OsservaBiella 2022. Link: https://www.osservabiella.it/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/BIELLA_PDF_completo_LINK-2.pdf

FOREIGN CITIZENS RESIDING

Source: OsservaBiella 2022

POPULATION STRUCTURE BY AGE GROUP, PROVINCE OF BIELLA

Source: OsservaBiella 2022

BIRTH AND MORTALITY RATE

Source: OsservaBiella 2022

BIRTH RATE: the average number of birth in a year per 1000 inhabitants

MORTALITY RATE: the average number of death in a year per 1000 inhabitants

The birth rate in the province of Biella is 5,2% and it is one of the lowest rate between the Piemonte provinces

AGING INDEX

PROVINCE OF BIELLA
289%

PIEMONTE AVERAGE
219,8%

The highest figure among the Piemonte provinces and it is 100 percentage points over the Italian average

Source: OsservaBiella 2022

OLD-AGE DEPENDENCY RATIO

PROVINCE OF BIELLA
49,3%

PIEMONTE AVERAGE
42,4%

It is 12 percentage points over the Italian average

HIGH SCHOOLS

LICEO (LYCEUM)

Liceo Artistico (2)
Liceo Classico (1)
Liceo Scientifico (4)
Liceo Linguistico (2)
Liceo Scienze Umane (2)

ISTITUTI TECNICI (TECHNICAL INSTITUTES)

Istituto Tecnico Economico (4)
Istituto Tecnico Tecnologico (5)

ISTITUTI PROFESSIONALI (PROFESSIONAL INSTITUTES)

Istituto Professionale Servizi (5)
Istituto Professionale Industria e
Artigianato (2)
Istituto Professionale (nuovi indirizzi)
(6)

Source: Regione Piemonte I numeri del sistema educativo

Link: https://www.regione.piemonte.it/web/sites/default/files/media/documenti/2023-10/I%20principali%20dati%20del%27a.s.%202022_23.pdf

FLOW OF ASSUMPTIONS BY TYPE OF CONTRACT ON A PROVINCIAL SCALE

■ Undetermined ■ Determined ■ Apprenticeship ■ Administration ■ Other

PROFESSIONAL QUALIFICATION

ECONOMIC SECTOR %

Source: OsservaBiella 2022

TYPE OF BUSINESSES AND MAIN SECTOR OF TRADE

	N of registered businesses	N of active businesses	%	VAR % 2020-2021
AGRICULTURE, FORESTRY AND FISHING	1447	1434	99,1%	-0,49
QUARRIES AND MINES	5	5	100,0%	0
MANUFACTURING ACTIVITIES	1991	1693	85,0%	-2,48
ELECTRICITY, GAS AND WATER SERVICES	93	82	88,2%	5,13
CONSTRUCTION	2544	2360	92,8%	-2,52
WHOLESALE AND RETAIL TRADE	3718	3400	91,4%	-1,79
TRANSPORTATION AND WAREHOUSING	202	172	85,1%	-6,01
ACCOMMODATION AND CATERING SERVICES ACTIVITIES	1167	962	82,4%	-1,13
INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SERVICES	301	277	92,0%	3,36
FINANCIAL AND INSURANCE ACTIVITIES	584	569	97,4%	2,34
REAL ESTATE ACTIVITIES	1786	1656	92,7%	-2,24
PROFESSIONAL, SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL ACTIVITIES	561	513	91,4%	3,64
RENTAL, TRAVEL AGENCIES, BUSINESS SUPPORT SERVICES	603	548	90,9%	0,37
INSTRUCTION	86	78	90,7%	2,63
HEALTH AND SOCIAL ASSISTANCE	94	83	88,3%	3,75
ARTISTIC, SPORTING AND ENTERTAINMENT ACTIVITIES	188	169	89,9%	4,32
OTHER SERVICE ACTIVITIES	814	793	97,4%	0,38
UNCLASSIFIED BUSINESSES	781	2	0,3%	0
TOTAL	16965	14796	87,2%	-1,1

Source: OsservaBiella 2022

EXPORT FLOW BY PRODUCT TYPE

Source: OsservaBiella 2022

AWARDS AND RECOGNITIONS

Awards have been recognised to cities within the Province, in particular to city of Biella:

Biella is a "UNESCO Creative city" (2019)

Biella is "Alpine Town" (2021)

PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION GROUP

The public administration group is composed as follows (31/12/2021):

Subsidiary foundations and CONSORTIA

CLICK HERE to find a complete list of the subsidiary corporations:

https://servizi.provincia.biella.it/openweb/data/files/Partecipate/PARTECIPATE_dlgs_33_art_22__2022.pdf

President

Vice President

Councillors

BARBARA COZZI	EDOARDO MAIOLATESI
CARLO GROSSO	FULVIO CHILO'
GABRIELLA DI LANZO	GABRIELLA DI LANZO
GIULIO GAZZOLA	LUISA NASSO
PAOLO RIZZO	MARIANO ZINNO

Only three corporations are included in the consolidated statements, these are (together with the services they provide):

The company deals with the enhancement and protection of energy sources and environmental resources, regular and extraordinary maintenance of stables, public lighting, remote control and training activities.

The company has been operating since 1986 in the field of public transport of persons, bus rental Gran Turismo and other commercial or mobility-related transport services.

The Agency is the institution responsible for the Public Administration of collective mobility throughout the regional territory.

Source: https://servizi.provincia.biella.it/openweb/pratiche/dett_registri.php?sezione=bilanci&id=23594&codEstr=P_OP

Source: <https://servizi.provincia.biella.it/openweb/trasparenza/organo.php?tipo=consiglio&CSRF=ala0b673e01d47e0d8c6ba1071e5e208>

CONSOLIDATED FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

CONSOLIDATED BALANCE SHEET (2021)

TOTAL ASSETS: 183.718.316,13

- Fixed Assets: 136.110.887,53
- Current Assets: 47.374.915,38
- Prepaid expenses and accrued receivables: 232.513,22

DEBIT/CREDIT RATIO

= 2.02597929

TOTAL LIABILITIES: 183.718.316,13

- Shareholders equity: 94.697.569,63
- Post-employment benefits: 529.489,33
- Retained earnings and accrued expenses: 31.314.214,55

RECEIVABLES

	808.518,07
	2.320.199,84
	5.786.019,93
	18.205.139,84
TOTAL	27.119.877,68

PAYABLES

	2.398.159,39
	3.124.453,00
	5.895.425,17
	43.526.272,76
TOTAL	54.944.310,32

In this link, more detailed statements are available, together with the auditors' opinion report:

https://servizi.provincia.biella.it/openweb/pratiche/dett_registri.php?sezione=bilanci&id=23594&codEstr=P_OP

CONSOLIDATED INCOME STATEMENT (2021)

	Positive components	Negative components	TAX and DUTY distribution
	1.644.591,38	6.373.786,55	-4.726.367,93
	1.768.921,14	3.627.506,00	-1.861.157,86
	15.093.265,51	15.453.588,31	316.133,14
	22.905.250,79	18.937.843,05	233.046,10
TOTAL	41.412.028,82	44.392.723,91	238.028,96

The operational management result in 2021 is **negative of 77.374,32**.

INVESTMENTS FOR MISSIONS (PUBLIC COMPANY EXPENDITURES)

The following table shows the institutional missions of Biella Province. They represent the public expenditures in response to citizens' needs. The table compares costs sustained in 2021 and those of 2020.

MISSIONS	2021	2020
1: INSTITUTIONAL, GENERAL AND MANAGEMENT SERVICES	9.169.016,43	8.289.941,96
4: EDUCATION AND RIGHT TO EDUCATION	4.577.515,97	3.047.847,99
5: PROTECTION AND VALORIZATION OF CULTURAL HERITAGE AND CULTURAL ACTIVITIES	73.248,00	79.839,41
7: TOURISM	55.908,76	105.725,97
8: SPATIAL PLANNING AND HOUSE BUILDING	155.334,01	155.584,24
9: SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND PROTECTION OF THE TERRITORY AND THE ENVIRONMENT	445.042,63	418.558,61
10: TRANSPORTS AND RIGHT TO MOBILITY	8.286.848,46	6.541.805,16
11: CIVIL RESCUE	10.670,29	54.352,84
12: SOCIAL RIGHTS, SOCIAL POLICIES AND FAMILY	5.400,00	5.755,71
16: AGRICULTURE, AGRI-FOOD POLICIES AND FISHING	456.111,02	420.933,76
17: ENERGY AND DIVERSIFICATION OF ENERGY SOURCES	159.003,81	139.732,54
20: PROVIDENCE FUNDS	-	44.482,00
50: PUBLIC DEBT	400.801,73	461.070,31
TOTAL MISSION EXPENDITURE	23.794.901,11	19.810.112,5

Source: Provincia di Biella.

Link: https://apbiella.soluzionipa.it/openweb/pratiche/dett_registri.php?sezione=bilanci&id=23277&codEstr=P_OP (Stato patrimoniale e conto economico 2021, pagg. 1-12)

https://apbiella.soluzionipa.it/openweb/pratiche/dett_registri.php?sezione=bilanci&id=22516&codEstr=P_OP (Prospetto costi per missione)

It must be considered that every year Biella Province estimates a fixed amount for two other specific missions: financial advances (60) and services for third parties (99).

In the budgeted financial statement of 2021, the estimated amount for Mission 60 is €5.000.000 and for Mission 99 is € 9.201.000,00. Nevertheless these costs do not appear within the actual expenditures sustained reported in year 2021 and 2020.

ESTIMATED BUDEGET

The estimated budget is related to years 2022, 2023 and 2024. In the table below, previsions about future expenditures for missions are listed.

MISSIONS	2022	2023	2024
1: INSTITUTIONAL, GENERAL AND MANAGEMENT SERVICES	3.881.858,00	3.906.458,00	3.904.958,00
4: EDUCTION AND RIGHT TO EDUCTION	7.707.690,46	4.356.690,46	3.468.090,00
5: PROTECTION AND VALORIZATION OF CULTURAL HERITAGE AND CULTURAL ACTIVITIES	132.658,96	130.500,00	130.500,00
6. YOUTH POLICIES, SPORT AND FREE TIME	0,00	0,00	0,00
7: TOURISM	43.700,00	43.700,00	43.700,00
8: SPATIAL PLANNING AND HOUSE BUILDING	155.855,00	155.855,00	155.855,00
9: SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND PROTECTION OF THE TERRITORY AND THE ENVIRONMENT	466.113,00	463.063,00	463.063,00
10: TRANSPORTS AND RIGHT TO MOBILITY	10.235.636,44	9.194.361,28	13.880.816,20
11: CIVIL RESCUE	57.938,00	7.938,00	7.938,00
12: SOCIAL RIGHTS, SOCIAL POLICIES AND FAMILY	7.000,00	7.000,00	7.000,00
15: POLICIES FOR WORK AND PROFESSIONAL TRAINING	0,00	0,00	0,00
16: AGRICULTURE, AGRI-FOOD POLICIES AND FISHING	426.735,00	414.235,00	414.235,00
17: ENERGY AND DIVERSIFICATION OF ENERGY SOURCES	143.600,00	138.600,00	136.600,00
20: PROVIDENCE FUNDS	89.530,16	111.597,25	111.997,25
50: PUBLIC DEBT	3.775.179,00	3.827.364,75	3.852.464,75
60. FINANCE ADVANCES	5.000.000,00	5.000.000,00	5.000.000,00
99. SERVICES FOR THIRD PARTIES	5.201.000,00	5.201.000,00	5.201.000,00
TOTAL MISSION EXPENDITURE	37.324.494,02	32.958.362,74	36.778.217,20

RANKING AND POSITIONING

According to Il Sole 24 ore analysis, the Province of Biella is at the 65th place in Italy for quality of life. The analysis is based on 6 parameters that analyze different indicators:

1. Wealth and consumption
2. Justice and security
3. Environment and services
4. Demography and society
5. Business and work
6. Culture and leisure

65th place in Italy for quality of life - GENERAL CLASSIFICATION

YEAR	1ST PLACE	BEFORE BIELLA	BIELLA	AFTER BIELLA	LAST PLACE
2021	TRIESTE	LUCCA	59TH PLACE	PAVIA	CROTONE
2020	BOLOGNA	CHIETI	57TH PLACE	VITERBO	CROTONE
2019	MILANO	LUCCA	55TH PLACE	TERAMO	CALTANISSETTA

12th place in Italy for wealth and consumption

YEAR	1ST PLACE	BEFORE BIELLA	BIELLA	AFTER BIELLA	LAST PLACE
2021	MILANO	BOLOGNA	5TH PLACE	TRENTO	CROTONE
2020	BOLOGNA	BOLOGNA	2ND PLACE	MILANO	CROTONE
2019	AOSTA	BOLOGNA	2ND PLACE	REGGIO EMILIA	SALERNO

59th place in Italy for justice and security

YEAR	1ST PLACE	BEFORE BIELLA	BIELLA	AFTER BIELLA	LAST PLACE
2021	PORDENONE	VARESE	33TH PLACE	VERBANO-CUSIO-OSSOLA	FOGGIA
2020	ORISTANO	NUORO	36TH PLACE	SASSARI	FIRENZE
2019	ORISTANO	SIENA	44TH PLACE	CAGLIARI	MILANO

Source: Analisi Qualità della Vita Il Sole 24 Ore. Link: <https://lab24.ilsole24ore.com/qualita-della-vita/Torino>

63th place in Italy for environment and services

YEAR	1ST PLACE	BEFORE BIELLA	BIELLA	AFTER BIELLA	LAST PLACE
2021	ORISTANO	ALESSANDRIA	82TH PLACE	ENNA	CROTONE
2020	MILANO	ORISTANO	68TH PLACE	TERAMO	CALTANISSETTA
2019	TRENTO	ASTI	63TH PLACE	PAVIA	ALESSANDRIA

84th place in Italy demography and society

YEAR	1ST PLACE	BEFORE BIELLA	BIELLA	AFTER BIELLA	LAST PLACE
2021	BOLOGNA	ENNA	88TH PLACE	FOGGIA	ALESSANDRIA
2020	CAGLIARI	GENOVA	98TH PLACE	LUCCA	ALESSANDRIA
2019	BOLZANO	IMPERIA	100TH PLACE	ROVIGO	SAVONA

94th place in Italy for business and work

YEAR	1ST PLACE	BEFORE BIELLA	BIELLA	AFTER BIELLA	LAST PLACE
2021	MILANO	ASTI	49TH PLACE	FERMO	CROTONE
2020	TRIESTE	CREMONA	66TH PLACE	POTENZA	CALTANISSETTA
2019	MILANO	MACERATA	35TH PLACE	GORIZIA	CALTANISSETTA

67th place in Italy for culture and leisure

YEAR	1ST PLACE	BEFORE BIELLA	BIELLA	AFTER BIELLA	LAST PLACE
2021	TRIESTE	ASTI	70TH PLACE	VITERBO	CROTONE
2020	RIMINI	FERMO	55TH PLACE	VENEZIA	CROTONE
2019	RIMINI	VARESE	48TH PLACE	TERAMO	ENNA

Source: Analisi Qualità della Vita Il Sole 24 Ore

PARAMETERS

The following are a series of parameters aimed at explaining the position of the Province of Biella in 2021 - between parentheses the location of the Province of Biella in the ranking compared to the 107 Italian provinces

WEALTH AND CONSUMPTION

-
- Population with active financing: **44%** (46/107)
 - Average house sales price: **€1.350** (60/107)
 - Bank deposits of consumer families: **€21.091,90** (38/107)
 - Spending of households on the consumption of durable goods: **€2.926** (4/107)

DEMOGRAPHY AND SOCIETY

-
- Birth rate: **5 live births every 1.000 inhabitants** (104/107)
 - Life expectancy at birth: **81,20 years** (87/107)
 - General medical practitioners: **8,15 every 10.00 inhabitants** (51/107)
 - Years of study: **10,23** (72/107)

JUSTICE AND SECURITY

All the data in this section are expressed in terms of complaints every 100.000 inhabitants

-
- Drug-related crimes: **77,42** (96/107)
 - Crime rate: **2517,40** (39/107)
 - Extortions: **14,34** (64/107)
 - Money laundering: **1,15** (23/107)

BUSINESS AND WORK

-
- Employment rate: **71,30%** (29/107)
 - Foreign companies: **0,07%** (82/107)
 - Export share of GDP: **35,11%** (40/107)
 - Youth entrepreneurship: **0,07%** (103/107)
 - Young who don't work or study: **19,40%** (51/107)

ENVIRONMENT AND SERVICES

-
- Air quality based on Pm10: **50,34 µg/m3**(65/107)
 - Bicycle lanes per 100 inhabitants: **8,50 m** (41/107)
 - Electricity from renewable sources: **570,88 Kwh** (40/107)
 - Waste separation: **0,72** (22/107)

CULTURE AND LEISURE

-
- Cultural offer: **14,08 shows every 1.000 inhabitants** (90/107)
 - Gyms, swimming pools and thermal facilities: **2,27 every 10.000 inhabitants** (35/107)
 - Libraries: **5.82 every 100 thousand inhabitants** (79/107)
 - Museum heritage: **0,22 every 100 km²** (83/107)

*Source: Analisi Qualità della Vita Il Sole 24 Ore

EUROPEAN PROJECTS

OFFICE EUROPE

In the province of Biella there has been established a place where ideas can be sparked and gathered to help with the creation and execution of international projects.

In here chances on a national and international scale can be found through web searches. It is possible to constant monitor the main information channels while giving updates on a regular basis. New ideas can be promoted and design to local governments, municipalities, universities, schools, and other institutions in the area interested in trying out European projects. Advice can be given on the beginning of the design and aiding in the project presentations. It is also useful for energizing the region and connecting it to opportunities that are already present but frequently difficult to find, the Office Europe encourages the design of programs and initiatives to support the development of skills.

REALIZATION OF PNRR MEASURES

In order to coordinate what is happening on the territory in regard to the PNRR, the Province of Biella, acting as a large area entity, formed a Regia Cabin - Office Europe of the Province of Biella.

The interventions relate to:

- Safeguarding and re-qualification of schools - MEASURE 4 - Component 1 - Investment 3.3
- Measures for the management of the risk of flooding and for the reduction of the hydrogeological risk - Measure 2 - Composant 4 -
- Investments 2.1b Extension of the use of national digital identity platforms - CIE SPID - Measure 1.4.4

The realization of European projects are in line with one of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals set by the Agenda 2030, specifically with the **SDG number 16**.

The most relevant point in the latter concerns firstly the promotion of justice together with equal accessibility to it. They also refer to it the creation of transparent and accountable institutions by increasing the participation in global governance and ensuring representative decision making. Another important aspect relates to a substantial reduction in corruption and bribery along with the prevention of violence, terrorism and crime.

Source: Provincia di Biella

Link: <https://www.provincia.biella.it/aree-tematiche/attuazione-misure-pnrr>
<https://www.provincia.biella.it/aree-tematiche/ufficio-europa>

SOCIAL POLICIES

The Piedmont Region has given the Province of Biella the following responsibilities in terms of social policies:

- Administration of the Provincial Office of Public Welfare, including support responsibilities in favour of the subjects whom the judicial authority has delegated the exercise of the guardianship, custodial, and support administrator powers
- Delegation of the appointment of the members of the board of directors of the IPAB (Public institute of assistance and charity) until the transformation of IPABs into public companies of services to the person or into legal persons of private law when this is of regional competence
- Support for the integration of foreign citizens
- Identification of needs of anti-violence centers and planning of the centers' location on the basis of the proposals received from local authorities, individuals and associates
- Preparation of lifelong training projects and organization of courses for those working in the facilities
- Maintenance functions of the historical archive of maternity and childcare functions
- Collection, archiving and storage of the so-called "buste chiuse" (closed busts) relating to the anagraphic data of the woman who exercised the right to privacy about the childbirth and the non-recognition of her birth.

This policy is strictly related to first SDG from the Agenda 2030, whose objective is to reach quality instruction.

In particular it aims to:

- By 2030, eradicate extreme poverty worldwide
- By 2030, reduce at least by half the proportion of men, women and children of all ages living in poverty in all its dimensions according to national definitions
- Implement nationally appropriate social protection systems and measures for all
- By 2030, ensure that everyone, especially the poor and the most vulnerable, has equal access to economic resources, basic services, ownership and control over land and other forms of property, inheritance, natural resources, appropriate new technology and financial services

Source: Provincia di Biella

Link: <https://www.provincia.biella.it/aree-tematiche/politiche-sociali-giovanili-pari/politiche-sociali>

IRIS CONSORTIUM

The Inter-Communal Consortium of Socio-Assistencial Services (I.R.I.S.) is an instrumental entity of the 41 municipalities of Biella Province, which focuses on programming, coordinating and managing of services articulated on a supra-communal area and of matters of health importance

INTERVENTIONS REALIZED:

ADOPTIONS: 14
 CUSTODIES: 86
 ECONOMIC ASSISTANCE: 1438
 HOUSE ASSISTANCE: 1187
 JOB PLACEMENT: 63

Source: I servizi sociali territoriali in cifre, Regione Piemonte

HOUSING FIRST AND HOUSING LED PROJECTS

 Housing First aims at giving access to a stable, safe and comfortable home to people who experienced long-term homelessness.

 Housing Led instead refers to services aimed at housing insertion, but of lower intensity, duration and intended for non-chronic people. The objective is to make the person able in the short term to relocate to the world of work and to find a home in autonomy

Source: OsservaBiella 2022

JUDGEMENT ON FUNCTIONING OF SOCIO-ASSISTENTIAL SERVICES

The following data refer to 2021, the answers to the survey were collected from a sample of 50 individuals

Source: Ires Piemonte - indagine Clima di opinione

EDUCATIONAL POLICIES

The Province of Biella takes care of the regular functioning of the network of Secondary Institutes by:

- programming of the use of the buildings in relation to the changing needs of the individual schools and their periodic reorganization
- defining, in agreement with the school institutions, the activation of new directions of study in the high school and the dimensioning of the institutions (institution, aggregation, suppression) through the preparation of the provincial annual plan for the organization of the school network
- supporting interventions for school integration of disabled students as well as initiatives and projects of particular educational and cultural interest
- ensuring the transportation of students for attendance to lessons
- managing funding for school building interventions

In addition, during the academic year 2021-2022, the Province supported the project "Diritto allo studio", which guarantees individuals of all school levels the right to study.

Specifically, the Province decided to:

- carry out educational support activities for students with disabilities
- continue the L.I.S. (Italian Sign Language) project to ensure the inclusion of audiolesians through the guidance of an interpreter
- ensure transportation for students with disabilities attending secondary schools
- assign special attractions for secondary public schools

With regard to the University, the Province supports, within the budget availability, the courses traditionally activated at the headquarters of Biella di Città Studi, putting as its main and further goal the development of the university center in Biella and the qualitative upgrading of the local educational offer.

This policy is strictly related to fourth SDG from the Agenda 2030 whose objective is to reach quality instruction.

Source: Provincia di Biella

Links: <https://www.provincia.biella.it/aree-tematiche/rete-scolastica>

<https://www.provincia.biella.it/aree-tematiche/rete-scolastica/diritto-allo-studio>

In particular it aims to:

- ensure that all girls and boys complete free, equitable and quality primary and secondary education leading to relevant and effective learning outcomes
- eliminate gender disparities in education and ensure equal access to all levels of education and vocational training for the vulnerable, including persons with disabilities, indigenous peoples and children in vulnerable situations
- build and upgrade education facilities that are child, disability and gender sensitive and provide safe, non-violent, inclusive and effective learning environments for all
- encouraging the acquisition of necessary skills for employment, dignified work, and leadership.

“DIRITTO ALLO STUDIO” PROJECT

THE NUMBERS

The following table displays both the total number of applications and the total amount of money asked from Biella Province schools to purchase teaching aids for disabled students. It also mentions the total amount of resources received by Città degli Studi di Biella (CTS) from the Italian Ministry of Education and Merit (MIUR).

No data of the academic year 2020/2021 are available due to COVID-19 pandemic.

	2019/2020	2021/2022
APPLICATIONS FOR TEACHING AIDS	21	26
TOTAL RESOURCES ASKED	€12.939,16	€17.921,78
RESOURCES RECIEVED BY CTS	€ 21.128,58	€ 24.220,46

Source: OsservaBiella

Link: https://www.osservabiella.it/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/BIELLA_PDF_completo_LINK-2.pdf

HOW TO SPEND RESOURCES

70% purchase and maintenance of teaching aids

30% achieve the goal of inclusion of pupils with disabilities, acquiring services aimed at the best use of the teaching aids supplied to school institutions.

CULTURE, SPORT AND TOURISM POLICIES

The territory of the Biella Province is characterized by the richness of environmental, historical-cultural and enogastronomic resources of considerable tourist interest. The Province aspires to promote the presence of natural-sports paths, and the many goods that, from textiles to food, represent excellence for the territory.

Culture is a fundamental tool for the development of the territory, beginning with the rediscovery of its roots and traditions, encouraging the spread of cultural and environmental heritage, and promoting the creation of thematic itineraries with tourist-cultural value.

Numerous historical monuments, shrines, churches, and the Sacred Mountains, recipes and castles, museums and ecomuseums, parks and natural reserves, and hiking trails are part of the Biellese cultural and environmental legacy.

The Province of Biella also supports sports culture by funding projects and activities that encourage a constructive and inclusive practice of sport and that understand how to mix sports features with the promotion of the Biella Province

The Tourism, Sports, and Leisure Service of the Province plays a significant role in ensuring that all of the above-mentioned areas can become economic growth opportunities for the territory by dealing with:

- notifications of openings, closings, and changes in tourism agencies
- examination of eligibility for the practice of tourist professions
- registration of the presence at the reception facilities
- annotation in the lists of tourism professions of the mandatory updating occurred

These policies, especially the ones related to sports practice, are strictly related to the **third SDG** from the Agenda 2030, whose objective is to ensure **healthy lives and promote well-being** for all at all ages.

In particular, it aims at:

- end preventable deaths of newborns and children under 5 years of age
- reduce by one-third premature mortality from non-communicable diseases through prevention and treatment and promote mental health and well-being

CULTURE - 2021 NUMBERS

MUSEUMS AND CULTURAL GOODS

The comparison with previous years must take into account that, due to the measures planned to deal with the Covid emergency, the museums and cultural property in the Province were closed to the public for 137 days in 2020 and for 95 days in 2021

MUSEUMS: **19**

TICKETS SOLD: **54.789**

OTHER YEARS DATA: 38.047 (2020), 96.059 (2019)

MOVIE THEATERS

The year 2021 for cinema has begun at the mark of closures: all Piedmont movie theaters remained closed to the public until the 25th of April. The decline recorded in the province of Biella is in line with the results obtained by the cinemas at the national level

MOVIE THEATERS: **3**

TICKETS SOLD: **43.969 (2021)**

OTHER YEARS DATA: 53.868 (2020), 166.189 (2019)

LIBRARIES

BiblioBi - Sistema Bibliotecario Biellese is the libraries management system of the Biella Province and it includes 48 libraries present in the territory. The followings are the data collected of 2021:

TOTAL MATERIAL AVAILABLE: **343.951**

TOTAL MATERIALS BORROWED BY USERS: **77.892**

TOTAL ANNUAL ACCESS TO THE FACILITIES: **8.038**

TOTAL SPENDING: **183.777,52**

Source: Osservatorio Culturale del Piemonte

Link: https://ocp.piemonte.it/doc/relazione_annuale/ocp_relazione-annuale-2021-2022.pdf

TOURISM - 2021 NUMBERS

ACCOMODATION STRUCTURES: **359**

SLEEPING ACCOMODATIONS: **6600**

N° OF TOURISTS BY ACCOMMODATION TYPE:

Source: Elaborazioni Camera di Commercio Monte Rosa Laghi Alto Piemonte

SPORT POLICIES - SCHOOL GYMS' SERVICE

THE SERVICE IN GENERAL

In Biella Province there are 290 associazioni dilettantistiche sportive (ASD), which are non-profit associations for sporting purposes.

The high number of sports' associations and the willingness to increase the possibility of practicing sports, led the Biella Province to grant temporary premises for the use of School Institutes' gyms owned or managed by the Province, with the consent of the Institute Councils.

The use of premises in school buildings, during extracurricular hours, was intended for local entities, sports and cultural associations for courses and sports activities.

APPLICATIONS REQUIREMENTS FOR THE USE OF GYMS

Applications were submitted by 30/08/2021, for those activities that took place during the course of the whole school year

Applications were submitted with a minimum of 10 days in advance of the date of use, for these initiatives during vacation periods of the lessons.

The associations, entities or groups that submitted an application for the concession of classrooms or gyms attached to the premises owned or managed by this Administration, specified at the time of the application whether they intended to use also materials owned by the school

TARIFS: the concession in use is subject to the payment of hourly rates, as a refund of expenses

SUMMER TARIFF		WINTER TARIFF	
WITHOUT USE OF THE SHOWERS SERVICE	WITH USE OF THE SHOWERS SERVICE	WITHOUT USE OF THE SHOWERS SERVICE	WITH USE OF THE SHOWERS SERVICE
€6,00	€8,00	€13,00 OR €16,00	€15,00 OR €18,00

Source: Provincia di Biella

Link: <https://www.provincia.biella.it/servizi/sale-aule-e-palestre/aule-e-palestre>

YOUTH POLICIES

The Office for Youth Policy performs institutional duties such as administration, intervention programming, territory coordination, assistance with local planning, and monitoring.

The focus of youth policy is on young people's involvement, leadership, and participation. In order to satisfy their needs, the Province of Biella has chosen to invest in young people.

The objective was to work in the direction of an organic development of a set of opportunities for meeting on many issues, from access to employment, home, and study, to creativity, to prevention, to leisure. It was not intended as a point of arrival, but rather as a starting point.

All this, without forgetting the encouragement given to young people for launching their own businesses. The Office is also devoted to helping local authorities get funding and pursue possibilities on the national and international levels.

CIVIL SERVICE

The Civil Service is a volunteer endeavor that does not allow access to the military and the port of arms. This activity lasts for a total of twelve months, and depending on the projects, the commitment may be rigid (between 30 and 36 hours per week) or flexible (with a minimum annual set of 1400 hours).

The National Civil Service is divided into commercial and public organizations that work in a variety of areas, such as those related to immigration, administration, youth deviance, and disabilities.

The objective is to increase young people's knowledge of many social concerns and to involve them in active citizenship in fact it can be considered in all aspects as a year of personal growth.

The economic treatment (reimbursement of expenditures) is 433.80 Euros per month, with the option of completing tasks also abroad. Universities may accept educational credits for some initiatives.

There are several institutions on the Biella territory where this activity can be done.

All young Italian citizens with graduate degrees, aged between 18 and 29 years old, who haven't turned 29 at the expiration of the bidding period, can become volunteers.

You must sign the National Civil duty Volunteer Contract before starting your duty.

EQUAL OPPORTUNITIES POLICIES

The Province encourages the sharing of information about funding opportunities for the development of positive actions that value gender differences and support the balancing of family time and workloads. It contributes to the dissemination of best practices and works in partnership with the "Consigliera di Parità" to carry out the duties entrusted to it and to promote particular projects.

In order to stimulate and oversee the application of the principles of equal chances and non-discrimination between men and women in the workplace, the position of equality adviser was created. (D. Lgs. 11 April 2006, no. 198, and subsequent amendments). Interventions such as support for active employment policies, including training or promotion of equal opportunity policies are used to carry out this purpose. The advisers is useful for observing adherence to the concept of non-discrimination between men and women and identifying infractions of the laws governing equal opportunities.

This policy is strictly related to **fifth SDG** from the Agenda 2030 whose objective is to reach **gender equality**.

In particular it aims to:

- end all forms of discrimination against all women and girls everywhere
- eliminate all forms of violence against all women and girls in the public and private spheres, including trafficking and sexual and other types of exploitation
- eliminate all harmful practices, such as child, early and forced marriage and female genital mutilation
- recognize and value unpaid care and domestic work through the provision of public services, infrastructure and social protection policies and the promotion of shared responsibility within the household and the family as nationally appropriate
- ensure women's full and effective participation and equal opportunities for leadership at all levels of decision-making in political, economic and public life
- ensure universal access to sexual and reproductive health and reproductive rights as agreed in accordance with the Programme of Action of the International Conference on Population and Development and the Beijing Platform for Action and the outcome documents of their review conferences.

Source: Provincia di Biella.

Link: <https://www.provincia.biella.it/amministrazione/consigliera-di-parita>

It is possible to get in touch with the equality adviser in case of discrimination in:

- access to work;
- advancement of a career;
- harassment at work;
- having trouble returning from maternity leave or requesting parental leave.

INDIVIDUALS PERCEPTIONS OF GENDER DISCRIMINATION LEVEL

Source: Ires Piemonte - "Clima di opinione". The sample measurement in Biella Province was composed of 50 respondents in 2021 and 49 in 2022

WOMEN PERCENTAGE ELECTED IN PUBLIC OFFICES

From the graphs, it can be seen that the women elected in public offices in the province of Biella, increased considerably in 2021 (with respect to the previous years) as a result of the policies implemented

Source: data elaboration Ires Piemonte - Sisreg
Data refers to the percentage of elected women for municipal administrative positions

SUSTAINABLE MOBILITY POLICIES

PUBLIC TRANSPORTATION

The province of Biella performs a number of functions related to public transportation, including:

- operational planning and administration of the regional public transportation service;
- identification and financing of public transportation services in municipalities with a population of less than 30,000 inhabitants;
- integration of urban services with those of the provinces;
- funding of public services in areas with weak demand.

The planning and programming tools used in the public transportation area are:

- Provincial Transport Plan, which defines: the layout of the infrastructure networks and of the transport services of provincial interest and the distribution of funding between the local authorities for the implementation of this Plan;
- Three-Year Program of Public Transport Services, which determines: the areas with weak demand and objectives to achieve in terms of efficiency and efficiency in the organization and production of services.

TRAFFIC CIRCULATION

The construction and management of provincial roads, and the regulation of road traffic inherent to them, is one of the fundamental functions of direct competence of the Provinces.

In 2021, the provincial council updated the "Plan of reorganization of the provincial extra-urban viability" by specifying:

- the viability to be classified to the provincial heritage (tangenziale of Mongrando and Bretella Lancia-NSA12) as an integral part of the network;
- the provincial viability possibly declassifiable in agreement with other Entities (Comuni ed ANAS).

These policies are strictly related to the eleventh SDG from the Agenda 2030 whose objective is to make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable. In particular, it aims at:

- provide access to safe, affordable, accessible and sustainable transport systems for all, improving road safety, notably by expanding public transport
- enhance inclusive and sustainable urbanization and capacity for participatory, integrated and sustainable human settlement

CITIZENS OPINIONS

The following data were collected through a survey sample in the Province of Biella made up of 49 correspondents in 2022, by Ires Piemonte

PUBLIC TRANSPORTATION COINCIDENCES

TRAFFIC AND PEDESTRIAN ROADS

TERRITORIAL COVERAGE OF PUBLIC TRANSPORTION

Source: Ires Piemonte - Climate of opinion

SUSTAINABLE MOBILITY IN THE PROVINCIAL CAPITAL (BIELLA)

EXTENSION OF THE PEDESTRIAN ROAD SURFACE: **0,60 m² every inhabitant**

TOTAL CYCLING LINES: **8,68 km**

NUMBER OF PUBLIC TRANSPORT RIDES PER INHABITANT: **7**

This data is significantly below the average value of provincial capitals in Piedmont of 35,75

Source: Ecosistema Urbano, Legambiente

ENVIRONMENTAL AND WASTE MANAGEMENT POLICIES

The service seeks to encourage actions that **preserve and improve the flora and fauna** found in natural environments. This is accomplished by promoting specific programs as well as by organizing, managing, and training volunteers to conduct ecological surveillance. The province collaborates with the volunteer ecological guards to monitor the environment and to offer information and educational opportunities.

One of the activity performed by the Provincial Administration of Biella is the "**Air Quality and Energy Resources**" service. It is active in the Environmental Protection area, deals with all institutional activities that permit compliance with the current regulatory framework for the protection of the air from all kinds of encoded pollutants.

In particular, the scope of activity of this service can be considered to be divided into the following functions:

- The granting of authorizations for activities that release emissions into the atmosphere, the establishment of emission values, specifications, techniques for sampling and analyzing emissions, and standards for determining whether the measured values comply with the limit values. Regulatory Framework of Reference: Environmental regulations. Published in Gazz. Uff. 14 April 2006, no. 88, S.O.) - D.Lgs. 3-4-2006 No. 152 (Part V).
- Protection of the public from changes brought on by noise pollution caused by anthropogenic activities, in accordance with the specific responsibilities given to the provinces by article 4 of L.R. 20-10-2000 no. 52.

In the application of these policies, the following SDGs are applied: 6, 7, 12, 13, 14 and 15. These sustainable development goals aim to put in the first place the preservation of the environment and its creatures together with ensuring availability to its natural resources ensuring a "green" consumption. In particular:

- SDG 6: ensure availability, sustainable management of water and sanitation for all
- SDG 7: ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all
- SDG 12: ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns
- SDG 13: take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts
- SDG 14: conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development
- SDG 15: protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss.

NUMBER OF PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEM INSTALLED

BIELLA PROVINCE

with a percentage variation from 2019 to 2020 equal to 11.78%

ITALY

with a percentage variation from 2019 to 2020 equal to 15.45%

WATER CONSUMPTION AND DISPERSION

BIELLA PROVINCE

AVERAGE VALUE IN OTHER PROVINCES

Average **water consumption** for domestic use (in litres) for inhabitant

PRODUCTION AND RECYCLING OF URBAN WASTE

In 2019 the urban waste production was around **81.958 tons**. The separate collection amount was around **68.6%** of the one produced.

In 2020 the urban waste production was around **80.147 tons**. The separate collection amount was around **67.4%** of the one produced.

Source: data elaboration Ispra, "Rapporti rifiuti urbani"

METHODOLOGICAL NOTE

This Popular Annual Financial Report is drawn up with the primary goal of ensuring clarity and readability for the different stakeholders of interest, by taking into account the characteristics of potential readers and defining the right graphical form and type of language used.

The data presented in this document are based on the 6 capitals: manufactured capital, natural capital, social and relationship capital, human capital, intellectual capital, and financial capital.

Firstly we looked for social demographic information about the province making comparisons with Piemonte region and Italy. Then a description of the context was provided by "The Sole 24 Ore" statistical evaluations, which shows how Italian provinces have developed in comparison to others. To follow the Public Administration group was described, including the subsidiaries and the governance group. The consolidated financial statements were afterwards analyzed in a very easy and comprehensible way by highlighting data regarding the consolidated group.

In addition, the Agenda 2030, which was endorsed by the United Nations member states, was employed as a framework for assessing the sustainability level of the Province with respect to specific Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In particular, SDG's have been taken into account in the analysis of the policies adopted by the Province.

In this report some specific data and information were not detectable and for this reason it has been omitted. In particular, the number of employees by age and gender for the public administration group was not found in the "amministrazione trasparente" section of Biella Province's website. Referring to financial statements no extraordinary transfers were found and no information about public debt trends were detectable.

For what concerns civic policies, these have not been included in the report since they compete to municipalities.

The most important sources used to complete this report were: the official website of Biella Province, OsservaBiella 2022 report, ISTAT Statistics and Sole24ore.

The group work for the realization of this report is composed by: Marchetti Alice, Maurino Indira, Munari Eleonora.

DISSEMINATION PLAN

The Popular Annual Financial Report (PAFR) serves as a key tool to engage the population in assessing and appreciating the performance of the Province administration. To ensure widespread dissemination of the information included in this report, a varied approach has been devised.

Firstly, to share the findings the report will be published in the European Journal of Volunteering and Community-Based Projects. This platform aims to present the report in November 2023, enabling a broader reach and exposure to a more diverse audience, including stakeholders interested in community initiatives and volunteerism.

Recognizing the importance of involving younger citizens, the plan also involves sharing the results on the social media platform of the Biella Province and in specific Facebook groups. This strategy's purpose is to reach the digital audience, where younger citizens are highly active, ensuring wider accessibility and engagement.

Moreover, for broader local coverage, the report will be sent to the newspaper "La Provincia di Biella." This collaboration will help disseminate the information to a wider spectrum of residents, including those who might not be active on social media or online platforms.

By implementing these diverse communication channels, the administration aims to maximize the reach and impact of the PAFR, making it accessible to a wide and varied audience, thereby fostering greater transparency and public engagement in the evaluation of the Province's activities.

REFERENCES

The references related to the specific topics are presented at the bottom of each page. However, in this section of the report, the overall most important references consulted to write this Popular Annual Financial Report are mentioned together with their respective links

Dipartimento per le Politiche Giovanili e il Servizio Civile Universale

<https://www.politichegiovanili.gov.it/>

Il Sole 24 Ore - Qualità della vita

<https://lab24.ilsole24ore.com/qualita-della-vita/Torino>

Istat

<https://www.istat.it/it/dati-analisi-e-prodotti/statistiche-a-z:-parole-chiave>

OsservaBiella 2022

https://www.osservabiella.it/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/BIELLA_PDF_completo_LINK-2.pdf

Provincia di Biella - Amministrazione

<https://www.provincia.biella.it/amministrazione>

Provincia di Biella - Aree tematiche

<https://www.provincia.biella.it/aree-tematiche>

Regione Piemonte - Database statistici

<https://www.regione.piemonte.it/web/amministrazione/finanza-programmazione-statistica/statistica/database-statistici>

Regione Piemonte - Database statistici

<https://www.regione.piemonte.it/web/amministrazione/finanza-programmazione-statistica/statistica/database-statistici>

United Nations - Department of Economic and Social Affairs

<https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

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